

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF 2-D BRAIDED PREFORMS FOR COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Two-dimensional (2-D) braided fabrics are widely used for composite reinforcement. In this paper, a general methodology is presented for analysis and design of 2-D shaped braids for composite applications based on process kinematics and unit cell geometry models. The process kinematics model describes the dependence of yarn orientation of braided structures on the machine setup and control during braiding, whereas the unit cell provides the geometrical relationship of braid angle to actual yarn geometry and fiber volume fractions along bias and axial directions. The usefulness of the models is illustrated with experimental and theoretical results.

Keywords: Braiding, Preforming, Composite Processing, Analysis, Unit Cell, Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

Braiding is an old textile technology, traditionally used for the manufacture of a wide variety of linear products ranging from cables, electrical insulators and shoelaces to surgical sutures. Recognizing the high level of conformability and the damage resistance capability of braided structures, the composites industry had found structural applications for braided composites ranging from rocket launchers to automotive parts to aircraft structures.

2-D braided structures are intertwined fibrous structures capable of forming structures with 0° and $\pm\theta$ fiber orientation. Although 2-D braids can be fabricated in tape form, the majority of braided structures are fabricated with a tubular geometry. Thickness is built up by overbraiding previously braided layers similar to a ply layup process. Braiding can take place vertically or horizontally, but a majority of the composite braiders are horizontal. A schematic drawing of an horizontal braider is shown in Figure 1. Although braiding is similar to filament winding in many ways, the major difference between braiding and filament winding is that braids are interlaced structures having as many as 144 or more interlacing per braiding cycle (or pick).

As in other preforming processes, the key engineering design parameters for composites are fiber orientation θ and fiber volume fraction V_f . The study of braid geometry in a systematic manner perhaps started with Brunnschweiler [1,2], who used idealized geometry and was concerned mainly with braiding angle and fiber coverage.

For composite braiding, a single equation has been used by the industry relating braiding angle θ to part parameter P , number of braiding carriers N , widths of braiding and axial tows width W_B and W_L , as follows: [3]

Figure 1. Schematic of tubular braider with gantry system.

$$\cos\theta = \frac{2N(W_L + W_B)}{P}$$

Following a similar idealization of unit cell geometry, the trend is to integrate the machine braiding parameters with the unit cell structural design as illustrated in Yang et al [4], Kruesi et al [5], Michaeli et al [6] and Du et al [7].

These approaches are adequate for prepreg or tape braiding without much change in yarn width and for the braiding of structures with constant cross sections. For braiding of dry tows and structures with variable cross sections wherein a dynamic interaction of the braiding machine and tow geometry takes place, there is a need for a more general representation of the kinematics of the braiding processes which allows for the tow width to vary over a limiting geometry. Accordingly, it is the objective of this paper to establish a generalized process model for 2-D triaxial braiding, relating braiding machine parameter process variables to the braid geometry. The kinematics model provides the relationship between the braiding angle θ and the braiding process parameters wherein the unit cell model relates braiding angle to yarn geometry to predict fiber volume fractions V_f along both the braiding and axial directions. The usefulness of this model is illustrated with some examples.

2. KINEMATICS ANALYSIS OF BRAIDING PROCESS

An illustration of braid formation over a shaped mandrel is given in Figure 2. Braiding yarns ($\pm\theta$) and axial yarns (0°) pass the guide plane which is usually the guide ring as shown in Figure 1, and deposit to mandrel surface in the deposit plane. The convergence zone starts from the guide plane with radius R_g and ends in the deposit plane with radius R_m , where all the yarns are in contact with the mandrel surface. The convergence length $h(t)$ indicates the position of the deposit plane relative to the machine, and the braid length $z(t)$ defines the position of the deposit plane relative to the reference point at the end of the mandrel, they are both functions of process time t .

Figure 2. Braid formation over shaped mandrel.

It can be seen from Figure 2 that, because of the symmetry, all the yarns deposits onto the mandrel surface at the same angle of $\theta(z)$ to the mandrel axis. This angle is actually the braid angle at the braid location z and can be obtained as:

$$\theta(z) = \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{R_g}{h(t)} \cos\gamma(z) \sqrt{1 - \left[\frac{R_m(z)}{R_g} + \frac{h(t)}{R_g} \tan\gamma(z) \right]^2} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $R_m(z)$ and $\gamma(z)$ are radius and half cone angle at the location z , respectively. The convergence length corresponding to the location z (at process time t) is determined from:

$$\frac{dh(t)}{dt} + \frac{R_m(z) \cdot \omega(t) \cdot h(t)}{R_g \sqrt{1 - \left[\frac{R_m(z)}{R_g} + \frac{h(t)}{R_g} \tan \gamma(z) \right]^2}} = v(t) \quad (2)$$

which correlates the convergence length $h(t)$ and thus the braid angle $\theta(z)$ to the machine speeds $v(t)$, the mandrel linear speed, and $\omega(t)$, the carrier rotational speed. The braid length is given by:

$$z(t) = z_0 + \int_0^t \left[v(t) - \frac{dh(t)}{dt} \right] dt \quad (3)$$

where, z_0 is the initial braid length at $t=0$.

3. UNIT CELL GEOMETRY OF BRAIDED STRUCTURE

The relationship between geometric parameters and processing variables of a particular preform structure can be established through the geometric analysis of its unit cell. The dimension and shape of the unit cell for a 2/2 triaxial braid is identified as a square shape with a width of W and a thickness of T , as shown in Figure 3. The cross-sections of both braiding and axial yarns are idealized to shapes of race-track, which consist of two half circles with a rectangle between them. The width-to-thickness aspect ratio of the yarns, f , is always larger or equal to 1 because of the compression over-mandrel during braiding. It is expected that for untwisted yarn bundles, $f \gg 1$; for slightly twisted yarn bundles, $f > 1$; for highly twisted yarn bundles, $f \approx 1$; and for metal wires, $f = 1$ (the race-track shape becomes circular).

Figure 4. Unit cell geometry for 2/2 braid.

Two yarn segments are contained in a unit cell along either $+ \theta$, $- \theta$ or 0° directions. Two groups of braiding yarns are interlaced every two yarns; the axial yarns are sandwiched between layers of $+ \theta$ and $- \theta$ yarns. We assume that the braiding yarns of $+ \theta$ and $- \theta$ groups are identical and have the same width (w_b) and thickness (t_b). There is always a gap (designated as ϵ) between each two braiding yarns of the same group so that the braiding yarns of the other group can intertwine from below to top or from top the below. In practice, the axial yarns may have different linear density or even different fiber materials from the braiding yarns, depending on application requirements. Therefore, the width w_a and thickness t_a of the axial yarns are not necessary equal to those of the braiding yarns.

Yarn Dimension. According to the definition of yarn linear density and the assumption of race-track yarn cross-section, yarn thickness, width and cross-section area can be obtained as:

$$t_{a/b} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{a/b}}{\kappa_{a/b} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + f_{a/b} \right) \rho_{a/b}}} \quad (4)$$

$$w_{a/b} = f_{a/b} t_{a/b} \quad (5)$$

$$s_{a/b} = \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + f_{a/b} - 1 \right) t_{a/b}^2 \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda_{a/b}$, $f_{a/b}$, $\rho_{a/b}$ and $\kappa_{a/b}$ are linear density, aspect ratio, fiber density and fiber packing fraction of braiding and axial yarns, respectively.

Unit Cell Dimension. As can be seen in Figure 6, the unit cell has three layers of yarns (+ θ , - θ and 0°) and contains total of six yarns (2 each of + θ , - θ and 0°). The thickness of the unit cell, which is equal to the braid thickness, can be written as:

$$T = 2 t_b + t_a \quad (7)$$

and the width of the unit cell is given as:

$$W = 2 (w_b + \varepsilon) \quad (8)$$

where ε is the gap between braiding yarns and is given by:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{2 \pi D}{N_b} \cos \theta - w_b \quad (9)$$

It is clear from the unit cell geometry shown in Figure 3 that the size of this gap ε is a good indication of braid density; the smaller the gap, the denser the braid. It is also clear that the size of gap ε cannot be smaller than the thickness of braiding yarns t_b . Based on these two considerations, we define the braid tightness factor, η , a non-dimensional parameter as an indirect measurement of braid density:

$$\eta = \frac{t_b}{\varepsilon} \quad (0 < \eta \leq 1) \quad (10)$$

Since $\varepsilon \geq t_b$, the tightness factor is within the range of 0 to 1.

Fiber Volume Fraction. In triaxial braided structures, axial yarns are free of crimp since they are always under one group of braiding yarns and over the other group. The expression for the fiber volume fraction of axial yarns can be derived as:

$$V_{fa} = \frac{\kappa_a N_a t_a^2}{4 \pi} \frac{\pi + 4 (f_a - 1)}{(2t_b + t_a)(D + 2t_b + t_a)} \quad (11)$$

Since all braiding yarns intertwine between the other group of braiding yarns as well as the axial yarns, a certain degree of yarn crimp is expected depending on braid thickness T . However, our experimental observations show that yarns have a high aspect ratio (usually in the range of 4 to 12) for untwisted roving bundles and that the effect of yarn crimp on the yarn length and inclination in radial direction is negligible. The general expression for the fiber volume fraction of braiding yarns is derived as:

$$V_{fb} = \frac{\kappa_b N_b t_b^2}{4 \pi \cos \theta} \frac{\pi + 4 (f_b - 1)}{(2t_b + t_a)(D + 2t_b + t_a)} \quad (12)$$

Total fiber volume fraction of the triaxial braid, according to its definition, is the sum of both fiber volume fractions of axial and braiding yarns, i.e.,

$$V_f = V_{fa} + V_{fb} \quad (13)$$

4. GEOMETRIC LIMITATIONS

Triaxial braid's geometric limitation is caused by the over-jamming of both braiding and axial yarns. As can be observed from the unit cell geometry shown in Figure 3, it is only possible for a braiding yarn to interlace two others if the gap space between these two braiding yarns is not less than the thickness of that braiding yarn, i.e. $\epsilon \geq t_b$, which is equivalent to $\eta \leq 1$. The same also applies to the axial yarns.

However, in practice it is very difficult if not impossible to predict jamming simply because the yarn aspect ratio is usually not a constant value during braiding. Instead, the aspect ratio automatically adjusts itself to form the tightest structure according to our experimental observations. In this case, we say that the braiding process operates under a **jamming** condition. However, there exist a maximum yarn aspect ratio f_{max} (at which yarn cannot be spread any wider) and a minimum yarn aspect ratio f_{min} (at which yarn cannot be squeezed any narrower). The values of f_{min} and f_{max} are functions of fiber material, yarn bundle size, fiber surface treatment, carrier tension, braiding angle, mandrel surface and shape etc. and may only be measured experimentally.

When $f > f_{max}$, yarns are impossible to spread any wider and their thickness cannot be adjusted any thinner while still maintaining the tightest structure. In this case, the braiding yarns are always under **pre-jamming** conditions.

When $f < f_{min}$, the value of f is indeterminable, because it is impossible for the actual yarn aspect ratio to be lower than that allowable in braiding. In this case, we would say that the braiding process operates under **over-jamming** conditions. The common phenomenon of over-jamming is that braiding yarns are not deposited tightly over the mandrel surface; as a result, when over-jamming occurs, the braid will be formed with a larger diameter than the mandrel cross-section at the deposit plane.

The criteria for the three braiding operation conditions and the determination of the aspect ratios of braiding and axial yarns under each condition can be obtained from the unit cell geometry and are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Jamming Criteria and Actual yarn Aspect ratio

Operation Condition	Criterion		Yarn Aspect ratio	
	Braiding	Axial	Braiding	Axial
Pre-jamming	$f_b > f_{bmax}$	$f_a > f_{amax}$	$f_b = f_{bmax}$	$f_a = f_{amax}$
Jamming	$f_{bmin} \leq f_b \leq f_{bmax}$	$f_{amin} \leq f_a \leq f_{amax}$	$f_b = \frac{2 \pi D}{N_b t_b} \cos\theta - 1$	$f_a = \min\left(\frac{\cos\theta}{t_a} (w_b + 2 \epsilon), \frac{\cos\theta}{t_a} (w_b + 15 \epsilon \tan\theta)\right)$
Over-jamming	$f_b < f_{bmin}$	$f_a < f_{amin}$	Indeterminable	Indeterminable

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the equations developed in the process kinematics and unit cell geometry analysis, the key relations between processing variables and geometric parameters of braids were established. The results of the geometric modeling can be represented in different ways, depending on specific technical needs. We have focused on braid angle (θ), total fiber volume fraction (V_f) and percentage of axial fibers (v_a) to illustrate the geometric relation of triaxial braided structures. The key process variables include the ratio of carrier-to-mandrel speeds ($2\pi\omega R_M/V$), initial convergence length (h_0),

ratio of axial-to-braiding yarn linear density (λ_a/λ_b) and the limiting yarn aspect ratios (f_{\max} and f_{\min}).

5.1. Relationship of Fiber Orientation and Process Kinematics

Using the process kinematics model, the fiber orientation of shaped braids can be predicted with the known machine speed profiles and machine setup (namely the guide ring dimension and initial convergence length). The simplest possible case was selected for demonstration purpose - a cylindrical mandrel being overbraided with the machine operating at constant linear and rotational speed. In this simplest case, the relationship between the braid angle and the process kinematics can be simplified to:

$$\theta(z) = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{R_g}{h(t)} \sqrt{1 - \delta^2} \right] \quad (14)$$

where

$$h(t) = \frac{v}{\omega} \frac{\sqrt{1 - \delta^2}}{\delta} + \left[h_0 - \frac{v}{\omega} \frac{\sqrt{1 - \delta^2}}{\delta} \right] \cdot e^{-\frac{\delta}{\sqrt{1 - \delta^2}} \omega \cdot t} \quad (15)$$

$$z(t) = z_0 + h_0 + v \cdot t - h(t) \quad (16)$$

$$\delta = \frac{R_m}{R_g} (\leq 1) \quad (17)$$

and h_0 is the initial convergence length when $t = 0$.

The distribution of braid angle along the mandrel length is shown in Figure 4, using Equations (14) to (17). In our calculation, we use $R_m = 0.02$ m, $\delta = 0.125$, $\omega = 0.36$ rad/s, $2\pi\omega R_m/V = 13.1$, and $h_0 = 0.24, 0.50$. Experimental comparison was also made using a 72-carrier braider with the configuration shown in Figure 1 and fiberglass roving yarns.

Figure 4. Braid angle along the braid length.

As can be seen in Figure 4, the braid angle varies along the mandrel axis even though both the braiding (carrier rotating) and mandrel speeds are constant. The braid angle at the beginning of mandrel ($z = 0$) is only determined by values of h_0 and δ but is unaffected by the machine speeds. As the braid length is substantially long (in our case, $z > 0.75$ m), the braid angle approaches a constant which is only determined by $2\pi\omega R_m/V$ and δ but is independent of h_0 . The measured angles are always smaller than the predicted values by about 5° at the steady state. The discrepancy between the predicted and measured values is due to the neglect of yarn interlacing which causes curved yarn paths.

5.2. Relationship of Fiber Orientation and Fiber Distribution

Using the unit cell geometry model, the fiber distribution along $\pm\theta$ and 0° orientation can be predicted with known braid angle and yarn properties such as the linear density, fiber density, fiber packing

fraction and limiting aspect ratios. The fiber distribution can be expressed by two parameters, the total fiber volume fraction (V_f) and the percentage of axial fibers (v_a) which is defined as the ratio of fibers in axial direction to total fibers in the braid.

Figures 5 and 6 shown V_f - θ and v_a - θ curves. In our calculations, assumptions were made that fiber material and fiber packing fraction are the same for both axial and braiding yarns, i.e., $\rho_a = \rho_b = 2.54 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ (for E-glass fibers), $\kappa_a = \kappa_b = 0.75$ and all the yarns have the same maximum and minimum yarn aspect ratios, $f_{a\max} = f_{b\max} = 12$ and $f_{a\min} = f_{b\min} = 4$, which are close to our experimental data for untwisted E-glass fiber bundles. The actual values of aspect ratio (f_a and f_b) and the status of braiding operation (pre-jamming, jamming and over jamming) of both axial and braiding yarns are determined as the level of braid angle increases from 0° towards 90° , using the criteria for geometric limitations provided. Other processing variables remain unchanged for all calculations, including: braiding yarn linear density $\lambda_b = 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1}$ (9000 denier), braid diameter $D = 0.1 \text{ m}$ and yarn numbers $N_b = 2$ $N_a = 144$.

As shown in Figure 5, for all levels of λ_a/λ_b , including $\lambda_a/\lambda_b = 0$ (biaxial braid), V_f first increases as braid angle (θ) increases under the pre-jamming condition while $f_b = f_{b\max}$ and $f_a = f_{a\max}$. After reaching their jamming braid angles, yarn aspect ratios (f_a and/or f_b) begin to drop, which forces the yarn thickness (t_a and/or t_b) to increase. As a result, the thickness of braid increases accordingly, which brings V_f despite the positive effect of increasing θ on V_f . The λ_a/λ_b ratio also has a significant effect on V_f . At low braid angles, while $f_a = f_{a\max}$, higher λ_a/λ_b results in higher fabric coverage and thus a higher V_f . However, lower λ_a/λ_b delays the onset of axial jamming at which V_f begins to drop.

v_a - θ curves in Figure 6 show that a higher λ_a/λ_b ratio will result in a higher percentage of axial fibers. The decreasing of v_a as braid angle θ increases can be explained by lengths of axial and braiding yarns within a unit cell; for a given unit cell with fixed width (W), the length of braiding yarns is not affected by the change of the braid angle, but the length of axial yarns becomes shorter when the braid angle increases.

Figure 5. V_f - θ curves for various λ_a/λ_b ratios.

Figure 6. v_a - θ curves for various λ_a/λ_b ratios.

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6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a general methodology based on the process kinematics and unit cell geometry models for analysis and design of 2-D shaped braids for composite applications. The process kinematics model describes the dependence of yarn orientation of braided structures on the machine setup and control during braiding, whereas the unit cell provides the geometrical relationship of braid angle to actual yarn geometry and fiber volume fractions along $\pm\theta$ and 0° orientation.

The key processing variables identified as the inputs to both process kinematics and unit cell geometry models include the ratio of carrier-to-mandrel speeds ($2\pi\omega R_m/V$), initial convergence length (h_0), ratio of axial-to-braiding yarn linear density (λ_a/λ_b) and the limiting yarn aspect ratios (f_{\max} and f_{\min}). The combination of these two models allows the prediction of braid angle (θ), total fiber volume fraction (V_f) and percentage of axial fibers (v_a) of triaxial braided structures, and thus provides the necessary information for the determination of the stiffness matrix of braided composites.

The unit cell geometry model established in this study is unique in the sense that it takes into the consideration the dynamic nature of yarn cross-section shape in braiding process and the geometric limitations due to jamming of braiding and axial yarns. It should also be noted that the unit cell geometry model is general in nature that it applies to either prepreg, tape or dry tow braiding. When this model is fully verified experimentally, it will form an engineering science base for the design of 2-D braided composites.

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